

CARMAN'S WHEAT-RYE HYBRIDS

Many Supposed Hybrids in the Rural New Yorker Series Show no Trace of Rye Characters—Only One Variety Originated from Real Wheat-Rye Hybrid—
Descendant of This is Probably Still Grown

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ELBERT S. CARMAN,¹ editor of the *Rural New Yorker* from 1876 to 1899, achieved, in addition to editorial success, some remarkable successes as a plant breeder. His work in breeding potatoes is probably the most noteworthy, although his work with wheat and his accomplishment of crossing wheat and rye are of no mean proportions. About the time that he took up his editorial work (1876 or 1877) he turned his attention to attempts to improve wheats, first by selection, second by changing spring into winter wheats, third by crossing, and last by hybridizing wheat and rye.

In the *Rural New Yorker* of August 30, 1884, is shown what is probably the first illustration (Fig. 14) ever published of a hybrid between wheat and rye. The cross, however, had been effected by A. S. Wilson, of Edinburgh, Scotland, who presented his results April 8, 1875, in a communication to the Botanical Society of Edinburgh, without giving any illustration. The plants secured by Wilson were sterile and the hybrid therefore was not carried further than the first generation, the matter then being allowed to drop. Carman apparently knew nothing of Wilson's experiment at the time his work was done. The hybrid secured by Carman furthermore produced a few seeds, with which experimentation was continued and from the progeny of which a variety was produced and disseminated.

This cross between wheat and rye was made in the season of 1883.² A head of Armstrong wheat, a popular variety later known as Landreth, and today as Martin Amber, was selected for the mother, because it is a beardless, hardy, prolific variety, as much so as any of the 250 kinds tested on the Rural grounds, unless it may be the Diehl-Mediterranean, a bearded variety of hybrid origin. The anthers were extracted by the aid of a pointed stick as soon as the head was out of the boot, while they were perfectly green, and the head was covered, bound with worsted³ for several days, when pollen of rye was applied to the stigmas from the point of a knife. This was repeated the next day, and the next, the head being again covered after each operation. Thus, before, while, and after he supposed the stigmas were receptive, pollen from rye was applied.

In this head ten more or less imperfect kernels formed which were planted late in September about a foot apart. Nine of these germinated, passed through the winter, and matured grain the next year, some being early, some medium, some late. There was no perceptible difference in the appearance of the plants during their early growth, except that some tillered more than others, but there were noticeable differences in the matured heads produced by the several plants.

From the illustrations and accom-

¹ For a short account of the life of Mr. Carman and some facts concerning his several achievements in breeding, see an article by Dr. E. M. East, in *THE JOURNAL OF HEREDITY*, Vol. VI, No. 2, pp. 65-67, February, 1915.

² The date, 1882, given in one account is evidently an error.

³ This is according to an account given in the same year, 1883, although in 1886, in reviewing the work, it is stated, "the head was then bound with tissue paper," which was temporarily removed for pollinations.

WHEAT-RYE

This is the first illustration ever published of a wheat-rye hybrid, and represents Carman's own work. It appeared as Fig. 339 in the *Rural New Yorker* on August 30, 1884. (Fig. 14.)

panying descriptions it is seen that the heads of eight of the plants produced, excepting that plant represented by Fig. 339 which will be considered later, differed from each other (1) in awn length, some having very short awns like the mother plant, others considerably longer awns, although none could

be considered as fully bearded; (2) in color of chaff, some having white, others brown chaff; (3) in size and color of kernels produced—this, however, may be due to difference in maturity; (4) in straw color, some having lead-colored, others golden-colored straw. These eight plants were in later accounts referred to as "those from the fertile plants of the original cross" and "the eight original plants resembling wheat (or the female parent) more than rye," while the remaining plant, Fig. 339 (reproduced herewith, Fig. 14) is referred to as "the nearly sterile plant" or the plant which "most resembled rye."

The best of the heads produced by these plants were selected for further growing. "The plot of about one-twentieth of an acre" where these were grown "presented the next season when the heads appeared, as varied an appearance as if kernels of all the most dissimilar wheats in cultivation had been sown." Among forms appearing were club-shaped and tapering heads, bearded and beardless heads, while the straw was yellow, dark brown or purplish. The size of heads, number of kernels produced, and size of kernels all were variable.

NO TRACE OF THE RYE

After careful examination of the available records and illustrations there appears to the writer no evidence that in these eight plants or in their progeny there existed any trace of rye. It is further apparent to one familiar with wheat-rye hybrids and with hybrids between different varieties of wheat that these eight kernels, supposed to have developed as the result of the fertilization of emasculated wheat flowers with rye pollen, must have actually resulted from fertilizations of wheat flowers with wheat pollen. How this fertilization occurred in a head supposedly emasculated before its pollen was ripe is not known, but there are several possibilities, among which is this: If, as seems probable, *worsted* was used to wrap the head after emasculating, wheat pollen may have sifted through this from other flowers nearby. It is well

A GRAIN OF ARMSTRONG WHEAT

This is the variety with which Carman made his wheat-rye hybrids; it now goes under the name of Martin Amber. Photograph much enlarged. (Fig. 15.)

known that the glumes of emasculated wheat flowers when not fertilized will remain open for some time and if not protected by pollen-proof covering will often be fertilized by pollen, probably air-borne. Again, some fault not apparent may have existed in the technique. Be that as it may, these eight plants show no signs of being wheat-rye hybrids, although at least some of them must have been hybrids between different varieties of wheat.

CARMAN'S ERRONEOUS BELIEF

Although these "eight original plants resembling wheat more than rye" cannot

be admitted to be actual wheat-rye hybrids, they were so considered by Mr. Carman. In all his later reference to them they are always considered to be hybrids of wheat and rye. Of all the wheats originated by him, the varieties first to be introduced, in 1889, included two descended through continued selections from these "fertile plants," these being Nos. 2 and 3. Both of these varieties were believed to be half rye, half wheat by parentage, though they had no appearance of rye in any respect. Introduced at the same time as these two wheats were four others, known as Nos. 50, 51, 53,

A GRAIN OF RYE

It will be readily seen that there are numerous small differences between this seed and that of wheat, and that the influence of rye would be clearly discernible, if present, in a hybrid. After carefully examining the descriptions of Carman's various supposed wheat-rye hybrids, Mr. Leighty reaches the conclusion that only one of his original nine was a real hybrid, the rest being nothing but wheat. Photograph much enlarged. (Fig. 16.)

and 55, originated by crossing different varieties of wheat. These were offered in August, 1889, by J. M. Thorburn & Co., of New York City, at 25 cents for a package containing twenty-five grains, or the collection of six sorts for \$1.

In 1890 these six varieties were distributed free to applicants by the *Rural New Yorker*, and the varieties of special interest here were named as follows:

"No. 2 (hybrid wheat-rye) has been named

Willits after the Assistant Secretary of Agriculture.

"No. 3 (also a wheat-rye hybrid) has been named Roberts after Prof. I. P. Roberts, of Cornell University."

Although the names applied augured well for these wheats, they apparently proved of little commercial value and so far as the writer knows, are not in existence as varieties grown anywhere today.

Turning now to the "nearly sterile plant," or the one that "most resembled rye" (Fig. 14),⁴ of the nine described above, it is evident from the illustration and descriptions that it was neither wheat nor rye, but had the modified characters of each. The shape and general appearance of the head, the arrangement and number of spikelets, and the glume characters were all such as are commonly found in wheat-rye hybrids. The culm resembled that of rye, except in color, having the whitish down near the head which never appears in wheat. This plant bore ten heads⁵ which produced but nineteen kernels, thus being nearly sterile. All of these characters combined allow no question of this plant being actually a hybrid between wheat and rye.

MUCH VARIATION IN PROGENY

The grains produced by this plant were carefully sown and fourteen or fifteen plants resulted, which passed safely through the winter and produced altogether 107 heads, the single plants having from two to thirteen heads. As shown by an illustration which Carman published, they are all rather long, tapering, slender, and half-bearded, with more spikelets than in wheat, in their appearance giving abundant evidence of rye relationship. The characteristic hairiness on the culm beneath the head is depicted in each case, although such hairs might theoretically be lacking in some of the plants in this second generation! Some of the plants were feeble in growth and partly sterile. Others were remarkably vigorous in growth, with strong stems and many heads. Some ripened with the earliest wheats, others continued green until

after the latest wheats had matured. The seeds varied in size, some being even larger than wheat, but as a whole they appeared to be wheat and yet had somewhat the shape of rye.

Rejecting all inferior heads, enough grain was saved from the best to plant a plat of about 1/30 (or 1/20) acre, that is, single kernels in the intersections of 10-inch squares. Regarding the crop grown Carman writes: "It is a matter of very great surprise to us that in this plat there is such a variety of heads that if evidence were suddenly placed before us that all of the varieties of wheat in cultivation sprang from accidental crosses between rye and wheat, we should accept it as in harmony with the appearance of these plants. The down does not appear upon the culms of some, while others are covered more thickly than the parent stems. The straws of some of the plants are three times the thickness of ordinary wheat straws. Some of the heads are beardless, others as much bearded as barley. Some heads are of the shape of Clawson, or the female parent Armstrong (tapering); others are club-headed, with and without beards. Some of the heads are compound. Our readers must remember that this twentieth of an acre of plants, so strongly dissimilar, all originated from a single seed, one of the ten kernels which four years ago was the result of crossing rye upon wheat."

The *New York World* in 1886 contained this description of the plants in this plat:

"Some of the plants were dwarf, not over 2½ feet high, with culms thrice as heavy as any ever seen in the pure wheats. Heads 7 inches long were not uncommon. Some were bearded heavily, others were beardless, and still others showed every intermediate stage. Some were club-headed, with breasts or spikelets densely crowded towards the top. Some bore compound spikelets, that is, two breasts growing instead of one, and the head partially double-breasted on each side of the rachis. Some heads were shapely, others twisted, with long, curly awns and culms as crooked as the heads. Some heads were larger and contained more kernels than any wheats we have ever seen growing in this climate. Others were feeble, narrow heads, scarcely 2

⁴ "The portrait is true, except that the beards are nearly twice as long as shown." (43: 557.)

⁵ "A later account states "14 heads" and "17 grains."

A WHEAT-RYE HYBRID

This grain is one of four produced on a wheat head from flowers cross-pollinated by C. E. Leighty. Although it is a genuine hybrid, it shows no traces of the influence of the rye (male) parent. The hairs at the top have been slightly retouched to make them more visible. Photograph much enlarged. (Fig. 17.)

inches long. The straws were all colors, from yellow to dark purple. They were of all thicknesses, from the size of rye to that of a small slate pencil. Some were densely downy, others smooth. Some were wiry and strong, others weak.

These plants were maturing variously, some with rye, some with wheat, while many were still perfectly green, with a good promise of not ripening at all. These strange plants, all from one seed, vary so remarkably, are so entirely different from either wheat or rye, that nothing short of seeing them can give the reader a good idea of them or enable authorities on grasses to intelligently consider the matter."

Long and faithful effort was expended in the task of fixing selections from the wheat-rye hybrids. In 1892 this statement was made concerning the progress up to this time:

"The illustration (Fig. 226) is a photo-engraving of typical heads of what we have alluded to as those hybrids

between rye and wheat which are distinctly neither wheat nor rye; in other words, they are new grains. For some years we despaired of ever fixing them. Seeds from bearded, long, narrow heads, as shown at No. 1, were just as likely as not to produce beardless, club heads as shown at No. 6, and all the intermediates as shown at Nos. 2, 3, 4, and 5, though the heads of the same plant varied only in size, the same as fixed varieties vary. Again, the downy stem was inconstant. Seeds from plants with stems as downy as the chaff of velvet-chaff wheat would produce culms without down, though we have never known a smooth stem to produce one with down. It will be remembered that the stems of the rye for an inch or so below the head are always fuzzy or downy, and that this peculiarity in the rye-wheat hybrids must come from the male parent, rye. The quantity of down, however, is variable. Some of the stems of the hybrids are densely downy or plush-like, while others are just like the stiffer fuzziness of rye. Here again the stems of a plant are all alike. It never happens that one or several stems of a plant are fuzzy while the others are not.

"The heads shown in the illustration are those of varieties which seem to be fairly well fixed. The beard or beardlessness, the downy stems, and the general shape are quite constant. They vary chiefly in the size of heads, some plants from the same seeds yielding plants some of which bear heads twice as long as others. Selections are now being made to secure the largest heads. The grain itself is just as distinct as the heads. The kernels are long, of a dark amber color, while there is so little starch in them that they seem almost translucent like horn. It is reasonable to assume that such grain would make a highly nitrogenous flour. Of this, however, nothing is positively known.

"The down extending 2 inches or more below the heads is not apparent in our illustrations."

In 1892 there were introduced three new varieties originated by Mr. Carman,

these being Nos. 1, 4, and 52. Nos. 1 and 4 are described as follows:

No. 1.—By parentage half wheat, half rye. Mother parent Armstrong. Heads compact, symmetrical, pointed, bearded; brown chaff. Three grains to a spikelet, eight spikelets to a side. Kernels hard, reddish or dark amber. Straw very strong and of medium height. As early as rye. Thought to be very hardy.

No. 4.—By parentage half wheat, half rye. Mother plant crossed progeny of Armstrong. Heads symmetrical and absolutely beardless; brown chaff. Three grains to a spikelet, eight and nine spikelets to a side. Dark amber kernels. Stems very strong. Ripens with rye.

No. 52.—Originated as a pure wheat cross.

From the data given it cannot be ascertained whether these two varieties were actually descended from the true wheat-rye hybrid or whether they were descended from the supposed hybrids as were No. 2 (Willits) and No. 3 (Roberts).

No. 1 apparently survived longer than any other of the varieties introduced up to this time, as it was offered to the trade by the seedsman introducing it up to and including 1898, while in the meantime the others had been dropped from the lists. It is not known to the writer that any of these varieties are now grown, although a variety called "No. 4" was seen growing in New York State in 1912, the characters of which agreed with the meager description obtainable of the variety.

In 1894 two further introductions of wheat varieties were made, these being No. 57 and No. 6. Although No. 57 was not originated as a cross with rye, it is perhaps the best of all introductions made by Mr. Carman, and a description is appended.

"Peter Henderson & Co., of this city, now offer for the first time two of our wheats which the firm has kindly named Rural New Yorker No. 57 and Rural New Yorker No. 6. The first is a heavily bearded variety, the parentage of which is one of our crossbred varieties fertilized with a crossbred of Velvet Chaff. The down ("velvet") upon the glumes is very light, though perhaps heavy enough to resist the green fly, but not dense enough to invite mildew, which is often an objection to Velvet

Chaff. We have raised our hybrids and crossbreeds only upon very small plats. From such trials, the No. 57 appeared to be a heavy yielder, with large, symmetrical, heavily-bearded heads, and tall wiry culms. It is a strong, vigorous grower, stools freely, and has never been winter-killed.

"The Rural New Yorker No. 6 is one of the rye-wheat hybrids, though all appearance of rye has disappeared except that the culms just under the heads are now and again downy as in rye. The downiness of the stem is variable. We have tried by selection for many years to fix it without any approach to success. Of all our rye-wheat hybrids, the downy culm is permanent in but one, and that resembles rye in several other respects. The Hendersons have found that No. 6 'succeeds and produces heavy crops on poor, thin land, where pure wheat could not be successfully or profitably grown.' This surely is a most valuable characteristic. Figure 165, page 630, shows the plant, one head, and several kernels."

THE ONLY REAL HYBRID

From this description and from a statement made elsewhere concerning its origin, it seems that No. 6 is actually descended from the true wheat-rye hybrid obtained in 1883. It is noteworthy for this fact, since it is the only variety introduced by Mr. Carman whose record, so far as determined by the writer, clearly indicated such origin. This variety is also still being grown, at least a variety bearing this name is now included among the wheat varieties of several experiment stations.

In common with the breeders of his day, Carman believed that the parents of a hybrid were equally represented in all self-fertilized individuals of subsequent generations. There might be variation in form but not in composition. He thought that by again fertilizing with rye pollen any plant of his first or later generations of wheat-rye hybrids, all intervening generations having been naturally self-fertilized, plants three-quarters rye by parentage would be secured. These plants or their

progeny in turn being again fertilized by rye pollen would produce plants seven-eighths rye by parentage. By continuing this process plants fifteen-sixteenths rye, and so on in the same fractional series, could be secured, the further generations thus all the time approaching pure rye in composition. The laws of Mendel were not then known.

Actuated by the desire to produce rye in this way, and thus, if possible, to throw some light on the origin of wheat and rye, Carman, with true scientific spirit, made the crosses as required by the theory, carefully year after year. A head on one of the eight "fertile plants of the original cross" was emasculated and pollinated with rye pollen in 1884. One kernel resulted, which grew and produced twenty or twenty-two heads on which were three kernels. This was apparently an actual hybrid of wheat and rye, the female parent being wheat, as pointed out above. It was considered to be, however, three-quarters rye. These three kernels grew and two produced plants, but their subsequent history cannot be accurately followed from the accounts given.

TRIALS COME TO AN END

A head of one of the hybrids most resembling rye was emasculated and pollinated with rye pollen in 1885. On this, seventeen kernels were formed, which resulted in fourteen plants the next year, these being considered as three-quarters rye. By following this

system with one (or possibly both—the account is ambiguous) of these lots of supposed three-quarter rye plants "several plants were produced with a supposed parentage seven-eighths rye," and at least one with a supposed parentage of fifteen-sixteenths rye. The supposed fifteen-sixteenths rye plant was entirely sterile, and the supposed seven-eighths plants were nearly all sterile. In spite of these discouragements the experimenter continued until finally he writes: "This trial has come to an end through necessity or through causes over which we had no control, viz., absolute barrenness of the latest progeny." The belief is expressed that "any endeavors to originate a hybrid which shall be more than three-quarters rye will prove ineffectual." No variety of supposed three-quarters rye parentage was apparently ever actually introduced, although one known as No. 11 was placed for propagation and introduction, but no later account of it is found.

In 1897, several years after his different wheats had been distributed, some one asked "Are there any of the Rural hybrid wheats that you believe to be ahead of all other kinds in hardiness and prolificacy?" The candid spirit of the man is shown in the reply: "No, we have not received any reports which would justify us in placing any of the Rural hybrid wheats above the popular kinds of today. . . . Of the crossbred wheats which have originated at the Rural Grounds, the R. N. Y. No. 57 is very promising." And so the matter stands.

Correction

Through an editorial blunder, the paper on Pollinating Fruit Trees, in the last issue of the *JOURNAL OF HEREDITY* was credited to Leslie Gordon Corrie. The paper was written by, and should have been credited to, Reg. W. Peters, director of the Queensland Acclimatization Society, Lawnton, Queensland, Australia. Mr. Peters was formerly

associated with William Bateson at the John Innes Horticultural Institution, Merton, Surrey, England, and took up the work in Australia last year. Members should note this correction in their copies of the August issue, in order that they may not repeat the error in making citations of Mr. Peters' paper at any time in the future.